

The job satisfaction of university teachers

Fatwa Tentama¹, Netty Merdiaty², Subardjo³

¹Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Indonesia

²Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Bhayangkara Jakarta Raya, Indonesia

³Faculty of Law, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jun 23, 2020

Revised Dec 16, 2020

Accepted Jan 10, 2021

Keywords:

Employability

Job satisfaction

Transformational leadership style

ABSTRACT

Employee job satisfaction is an important factor that can determine organizational productivity, and organizations need to pay attention to this pivotal aspect. This study aimed to empirically examine the role of transformational leadership styles and employability on employee job satisfaction. The participants of this study are 49 university teachers at the University of X Yogyakarta. The sampling is randomly chosen using a simple random sampling technique. In addition, data are collected using the scale of job satisfaction, the scale of transformational leadership style, and scale of employability. The data are then analyzed using multiple linear regression techniques. The results showed that 1) Simultaneously, transformational leadership style and employability provide a very significant role in influencing job satisfaction with $p=0.000$ ($p<0.01$); 2) Partially transformational leadership style provide a significant role on job satisfaction with $p=0.019$ ($p<0.05$); 3) Partially there was a very significant role of employability on job satisfaction with $p=0.000$ ($p<0.01$). Transformational leadership style and employability contribute 52.5% to job satisfaction. Employability contributed more dominantly to job satisfaction (35.8%) than the transformational leadership style (16.7%).

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Fatwa Tentama

Faculty of Psychology

Universitas Ahmad Dahlan

Kapas Street 9, Semaki, Umbulharjo, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Email: fatwa.tentama@psy.uad.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Human Resources have been recognized as an intrinsic part that directly correlated to the wealth of an organization. Humans are, therefore, the most important assets that must be owned by an organization [1]. Organizations use humans as a strategic tool of competence to achieve their goals, so it is important for them to pay attention to their employees' job satisfaction because it plays an important role in influencing organizational performance [2]. Employee job satisfaction determines their performance. It also influences the up and downs of employee performance and subsequently determines whether or not the organization's goals are achieved [3].

Job satisfaction is considered as an essential welfare index to note because it influences employee performance. Job satisfaction benefits are not limited to individuals but also extend to organizations and even to coworkers [4]. Another positive benefit of employee job satisfaction for organizations is that employees will be more motivated and committed to improving the quality of their performance [5]. Individuals who have higher job satisfaction will work more optimally and be more productive [6] so that with increasing

employee welfare, organizations will reduce operational costs because the impact resulting from employee job satisfaction is an increase in productivity in terms of quantity and quality [4].

Low employee job satisfaction can have an impact on high turnover in organizations [7]. Some researchers found that low employee job satisfaction can also impact the low quality of work produced [8]. In addition, low job satisfaction can also lead to low organizational commitment and high turnover [9]. Another negative side of the low employee job satisfaction is the declining quality and quantity of employee work results and the low involvement of employees working towards the organization [10]. A study revealed that a low level of job satisfaction within an organization reflects an organizational atmosphere where it is usually not conducive and will lead to turnover [11].

Job satisfaction is the result of job evaluation related to the possibility of achieving critical work values [12]. Job satisfaction refers to an individual's feelings or state of mind according to the nature of his work [2]. Job satisfaction is described as pleasant, positive feelings from the results of job evaluations based on individual experiences [11]. Job satisfaction is defined as work tendencies that involve positive feelings about work or positive perceptions during work practice and the absence of stress and anxiety during the work process [13]. Job satisfaction describes an assessment of an individual's positive or negative values regarding a job or job status [14].

One leadership style that is believed to be able to trigger the emergence of job satisfaction among individuals is transformational leadership [15]. Transformational leadership style can inspire and motivate individuals to make psychological changes, such as work stratum, desire for turnover, and excellence in work [16]. This leadership style is able to reduce or minimize conflicts within the scope of small teams and organizations more broadly. Low conflict is a means to foster job satisfaction in employees [17]. A study found that organizations that adopt transformational leadership styles tend to have employees with extra satisfaction and full commitment. Employees who are happy with their work will complete their tasks to the maximum, which ultimately leads to organizational effectiveness [18].

Transformational leadership style is described as a style where leaders will inspire their subordinates with ideas and morals to improve the performance of their subordinates to reach the highest level of achievement [19]. It is a leadership style that develops and maintains a control system by assessing creativity and innovation through performance measurement and an appropriate reward system [20]. It is a kind of a leader who supports their subordinates by increasing awareness of the interests, expected outcomes, and motivating subordinates by satisfying personal development in the organization's collective vision [21]. Transformational leadership style is a leadership style that focuses on inspiration, encouragement, and leadership by providing examples that can develop the potential of subordinates [17].

Employability is one of the factors that can increase individual job satisfaction, and employability will facilitate individual skills to get maximum and more satisfying results [22]. Employability increases confidence in solving problems. Various problems that can be solved will make individuals feel satisfied with the results and work [23]. It allows individuals to be more flexible in completing tasks and face challenges that can contribute to obtaining an adequate level of job satisfaction [24]. Individuals with employability will use their knowledge, skills, and personal attributes in work that enable them to get maximum results so that individuals tend to be more satisfied with their quality and work [25].

Employability is described as an effort to meet the demands of work on an ongoing basis by utilizing competence to the fullest [26]. Employability is the ability possessed by individuals to secure and maintain jobs [27]. It is defined as a set of skills, knowledge, and personal attributes that make individuals able to maintain their work and make a positive contribution to themselves, the organization, and the surrounding environment [28]. It also refers to an individual's ability to demonstrate the skills, knowledge, attributes, and attitudes to secure a job [29-31]. Employability is the quality and competence needed by individuals to meet the needs of the organization so that it can help realize the goals of the organization [32].

Based on the explanation above, the interrelationship between transformational leadership style and employability on job satisfaction can be described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The role of transformational leadership style and employability on job satisfaction

This study aimed to empirically examine the role of transformational leadership style and employability in predicting job satisfaction among university teachers at the University of X Yogyakarta.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research participant

The subjects in this study are university teachers at the University of X Yogyakarta, totaling 49 university teachers. Characteristics of the subject are as permanent employees, have worked for at least five years and have the status as a teacher or lecturer. The selection of subjects was carried out randomly using simple random sampling techniques.

2.2. Instrument

The data in this study are collected using scales, namely: job satisfaction scale, transformational leadership style scale, and employability scale. The job satisfaction scale is designed based on aspects of job satisfaction, according to Smith, Kendall, and Hulin [33, 34], namely: the job itself, salary, promotion, supervision, and coworkers. The scaling model used for the job satisfaction scale is the Likert scale model. Examples of job satisfaction scale items are: "When I ask a colleague to help me do a certain task, the task can be completed", "I am satisfied with the improvement in my progress", and "I feel comfortable working in this organization".

The scale of the transformational leadership style adopts aspects of transformational leadership according to Bass [35, 36]. It includes charisma, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual considerations. Liker scale model is also used for this scale. Examples of items on this scale are: "Leaders can express organizational goals in interesting and fun ways", "Leaders pay attention to every employee who has difficulty in his work", and "Leaders like to involve me in problem-solving".

The scale of employability is composed based on the dimensions of employability, according to Fugate, Kinicki, and Ashforth [37], namely: career identity, personal adaptability, social and human capital. It also uses a Likert scaling model. Examples of employability scale items are: "I share information with coworkers related to the job completion process", "I hope to get a job that suits my field", and "I am able to act flexibly in an environment that is less supportive".

2.3. Validity and reliability of instruments

The results of a trial analysis of 30 subjects on the job satisfaction scale obtained the results of the reliability coefficient (α) of 0.706 with a different item power index (corrected item-total correlation) that moves from 0.267 to 0.581. Valid and reliable items that will be used for research are seven items.

The results of the trial analysis of 30 subjects on the scale of the transformational leadership style obtained the results of the reliability coefficient (α) of 0.913 with different item power index (corrected item-total correlation) moving from 0.269 to 0.655. Valid and reliable items that will be used for research are six items.

The results of the trial analysis of 30 subjects on the scale of employability obtained the results of the reliability coefficient (α) of 0.821 with a different power index item (corrected item-total correlation) that moves from 0.289 to 0.510. The valid and reliable items that will be used for research are twenty items.

2.4. Data analysis

To analyze the data, the researchers use the parametric statistical method. Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 21.0, through multiple regression test techniques, which are statistical analysis techniques to determine the role of transformational leadership styles and employability in predicting job satisfaction.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Prerequisite test

3.1.1. Normality test

Based on the results of the normality test analysis listed in Table 1, it is known that the significance value of the variables of job satisfaction, transformational leadership style, and employability are 0.089, 0.086, and 0.530 respectively which have $p > 0.05$ meaning that each data is normally distributed. It can be said that each variable has a normally distributed data distribution.

Table 1. Distribution normality tes

Variable	Score K-SZ	Significance	Explanation
Job satisfaction	1.248	0.089	Normal
Transformational leadership style	1.253	0.086	Normal
Employability	0.809	0.530	Normal

3.1.2. Linearity test

Linearity test on transformational leadership to job satisfaction results shown in Table 2 obtained F linearity of 24.584 with a significance level (p) of 0.000. Meanwhile, the test on employability to job satisfaction obtained F linearity of 50.564 with a significance level (p) of 0.000, which means linear. Thus, there is a clear line that connects both variables linearly.

Table 2. Linearity tes

Variable	F Linearity	Significance	Rule	Explanation
Transformational leadership style	24.584	0.000	P < 0.05	Linear
Employability	50.564	0.000	P < 0.05	Linear

3.1.3. Multicollinearity test

The information in Table 3 shows that the test on both variables obtained a VIF value of 1.405 (VIF<10) with a tolerance of 0.712 (tolerance>0.1). Thus, there is no multicollinearity between the two variables.

Table 3. Multicollinearity tes

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Explanation
Transformational leadership style	0.712	1.405	No Multicollinearity
Employability	0.712	1.405	No Multicollinearity

3.2. Regression analysis test

It can be seen from Table 4 that the role of the transformational leadership style on job satisfaction is obtained partial value of 0.337 with a significance level of p of 0.019 (p<0.05), which means transformational leadership style play a very significant role in determining work satisfaction. The partial value between employability and job satisfaction is 0.514 with a significance level of p 0.000 (p<0.01), which means it plays a very significant role in employability.

Table 4. Partial hypothesis test

Variable	Partial	Significance	Rule	Explanation
Transformational leadership style to job satisfaction	0.337	0.019	P < 0.01	There's a role and very significant
Employability to job satisfaction	0.514	0.000	P < 0.01	There's a role and very significant

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis in Table 5, it was found that transformational leadership style and employability can simultaneously contribute to university teachers' job satisfaction at the University of X Yogyakarta. These results indicate that the first hypothesis is accepted so that job satisfaction variables can be predicted based on the transformational leadership style and employability. Simultaneously, the two independent variables contributed 52.5% to employability, and other factors could influence the remaining 47.5%. Other factors that affect job satisfaction include work type, organizational policy, supervision, administration, salary, and quality of life [2]. The contribution of the transformational leadership style to job satisfaction is 16.7%, and the contribution of employability to job satisfaction is 35.8%. It means employability contributes more dominantly than leadership style to job satisfaction.

Table 5. Simultaneous hypothesis test

Variable	R	R Square	Significance	Rule	Explanation
Transformational leadership and Employability to job satisfaction	0.725	0.525	0.000	P < 0.01	There's a very significant role

The analysis shows that the second hypothesis is also accepted. It means that the transformational leadership style plays a certain role in university teachers' job satisfaction at the University of X Yogyakarta. This result is in line with previous research findings, which found that transformational leadership styles are more able to provide job satisfaction for employees [38, 39]. The transformational leadership style directs

attention to the relevance of trust among team members, where it is considered capable of giving satisfaction to subordinates [40]. The transformational leadership style can shape the quality of the work environment with better results [41]. It refers to the process of interaction between leaders and subordinates with the aim of increasing the creativity and motivation of subordinates and hoping that it can provide employee satisfaction at work [42].

Transformational leadership encourages subordinates to make changes or innovations in themselves and the organization. Besides, this style focuses on increasing work motivation and employee confidence to be willing to contribute more to the organization so that leaders tend to be more actively involved with their subordinates, it is felt to make subordinates feeling satisfied at work [43]. Some researchers find that transformational leader behavior is able to explain important parts of job satisfaction. Individuals feel more satisfied when they have leaders who support their ideas and are open to other subordinates. Furthermore, transformational leaders are considered more inspiring to their subordinates [44]. Leaders with transformational style tend to be more valued by their subordinates because subordinates feel more comfortable and satisfied with supportive methods that their leaders have. This kind of leaders is willing to embrace, maintain and give confidence, which is proven to be helpful for subordinates to create innovation, individualized consideration, and broaden interactions which ultimately develop the level of competence [18].

The results of the analysis for the third hypothesis are accepted, which means that employability plays a role in university teachers' job satisfaction at the University of X Yogyakarta. This finding supports the results of previous studies which found that employability is responsible for the level of employee satisfaction [45]. Employability predicts a number of results that give satisfaction to their work [46, 47]. Individuals who have employability tend to have higher job satisfaction and achievement [24]. Employability has a positive role in helping individuals improve their skills in certain tasks, which allows them to respond by increasing job satisfaction [48, 49].

Employability has a positive effect on employee job satisfaction because the quality of employability allows individuals to proactively identify various job opportunities and choose the most suitable or most flexible in terms of work conditions [24]. Individuals with knowledge, skills, and experience are needed by organizations for the demands of their goals and make it possible to do work efficiently, so that individuals with employability have the opportunity to get jobs that they feel are satisfying, because individuals can choose conditions of work that suit themselves [50, 51]. Employability encourages individuals to control their careers, thus enabling individuals to fully control the things that can reduce their satisfaction at work [37].

This research can provide insight and awareness to employees and organizations. This research shows that transformational leadership style and employability can make employees to be more comfortable and satisfied with their work, but also can foster a willingness for employees to contribute optimally, as well as provide insights to evaluate themselves about the quality of their work. Organizations can consider the factors of informational leadership style and employability in selecting employees. The results of this study can also be used as a reference for compiling training modules specifically employability training which has a dominant contribution to dealing with employee problems in terms of job satisfaction at the University of X Yogyakarta. Thus, employees will contribute more to the organization with satisfying results for personal employees.

4. CONCLUSION

The transformational leadership style and employability are simultaneously able to predict university teachers' job satisfaction at the University of X Yogyakarta. The contribution of transformational leadership style and employability to job satisfaction is 52.5%. The contribution of employability to job satisfaction is more dominant than the contribution of the transformational leadership style.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Institute for Research and Community Service for granting permission and facilities to carry out this research. The authors also thanks to the lecturers and staff at the University of X Yogyakarta, who have contributed to the research process.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. I. Harris, A. M. Winskowski, and B. E. Engdahl, "Types of workplace social support in the prediction of job satisfaction," *The Career Development Quarterly*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 150-156, 2007.
- [2] M. S. Farooqui and A. Nagendra, "The impact of person organization fit on job satisfaction and performance of the employees," *Procedia Economics and Finance*, vol. 11, pp. 122-129, 2014.
- [3] D. Serrano and L. Vieira, "Low pay, higher pay and job satisfaction within the European union: Empirical evidence from fourteen countries," *Discussion Papers*, no. 1558, pp. 1-25, 2005.
- [4] M. Y. Chen, "Validation of the wood's job satisfaction questionnaire among Taiwanese non-profit sport organization workers," *Social Indicators Research*, vol. 94, no. 3, pp. 437, 2009.
- [5] Q. B. Baloch, "Effects of job satisfaction on employee motivation & turn over intentions," *Journal of Managerial Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1-21, 2009.
- [6] A. T. Hsieh and D. H. Wu, "The relationship between timing of tipping and service effort," *Service Industries Journal*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 1-14, 2007.
- [7] J. H. Larrabee, M. A. Janney, C. L. Ostrow, M. L. Withrow, G. R. Hobbs, and C. Burant, "Predicting registered nurse job satisfaction and intent to leave," *Journal of Nursing Administration*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 271-283, 2003.
- [8] L. H. Aiken, S. P. Clarke, R. B. Cheung, D. M. Sloane, and J. H. Silber, "Educational levels of hospital nurses and surgical patient mortality," *Jama*, vol. 290, no. 12, pp. 1617-1623, 2003.
- [9] S. Gaertner, "Structural determinants of job satisfaction and organizational commitment in turnover models," *Human Resource Management Review*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 479-493, 1999.
- [10] T. Velnamby, "Job attitude and employees performance of public sector organizations in Jaffna District, Sri Lanka," *Gitam Journal of Management*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 66-73, 2008.
- [11] N. Shahmohammadi, "The relationship between management style with human relations and job satisfaction among guidance schools' principals in district 3 of Karaj," *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 205, pp. 247-253, 2015.
- [12] F. Foroughi, H. Kharrazi, S. Iranfar, and M. Rezaei, "Job satisfaction and its affecting factors from the viewpoints of faculty members of Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences," *Iranian Journal of Medical Education*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 335-342, 2008.
- [13] N. Saraf, C. S. Langdon, and S. Gosain, "IS application capabilities and relational value in interfirm partnerships," *Information Systems Research*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 320-339, 2007.
- [14] M. S. Christian, A. S. Garza and J. E. Slaughter, "Work engagement: A quantitative review and test of its relations with task and contextual performance," *Persomel Psychology*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 89-136, 2011.
- [15] O. P. Salau, O. Oludayo, H. Falola, M. Olokundun, S. Ibidunni, and T. Atolagbe, "Integrated datasets on transformational leadership attributes and employee engagement: The moderating role of job satisfaction in the fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) Industry," *Data in Brief*, vol. 19, pp. 2329-2335, 2018.
- [16] H. Saleem, "The impact of leadership styles on job satisfaction and mediating role of perceived organizational politics," *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 172, pp. 563-569, 2015.
- [17] J. Kammerhoff, O. Lauenstein, and A. Schütz, "Leading toward harmony—different types of conflict mediate how followers' perceptions of transformational leadership are related to job satisfaction and performance," *European Management Journal*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 210-221, 2019.
- [18] M. K. Abouraia and S. M. Othman, "Transformational leadership, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intentions: The direct effects among bank representatives," *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 404-423, 2017.
- [19] M. D. Ensley, C. L. Pearce, and K. M. Hmieleski, "The moderating effect of environmental dynamism on the relationship between entrepreneur leadership behavior and new venture performance," *Journal of Business Venturing*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 243-263, 2006.
- [20] D. Jung, A. Wu, and C. W. Chow, "Towards understanding the direct and indirect effects of CEOs' transformational leadership on firm innovation," *The Leadership Quarterly*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 582-594, 2008.
- [21] T. T. Nguyen, L. Mia, L. Winata, and V. K. Chong, "Effect of transformational-leadership style and management control system on managerial performance," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 70, pp. 202-213, 2017.
- [22] N. Sümer, E. Helvacı and M. Misirlisoy, "Employability of psychology graduates and their job satisfaction in turkey: An online survey," *Psychology Learning & Teaching*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 189-195, 2013.
- [23] M. Y. P. Peng, C. C. Chen and H. Y. Yen, "A comparative study of the relationship among antecedents and job satisfaction in taiwan and mainland China: Employability as mediator," *International journal of environmental research and public health*, vol. 16, no. 14, pp. 1-17, 2019.
- [24] J. P. Gamboa, F. Gracia, P. Ripoll, and J. M. Peiró, "Employability and personal initiative as antecedents of job satisfaction," *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 632-640, 2009.
- [25] A. De Vos, S. De Hauw, and B. I. Van der Heijden, "Competency development and career success: The mediating role of employability," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 79, no. 2, pp. 438-447, 2011.
- [26] C. M. Van Der Heijde and B. I. Van Der Heijden, "A competence-based and multidimensional operationalization and measurement of employability," *Human Resource Management*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 449-476, 2006.
- [27] E. Berntson and S. Marklund, "The relationship between perceived employability and subsequent health," *Work & Stress*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 279-292, 2007.
- [28] N. Moreland, *Entrepreneurship and higher education: An employability perspective*. New York: Higher Education Academy, 2006.
- [29] L. Dacre Pool and P. Sewell, "The key to employability: Developing a practical model of graduate employability," *Journal of Education and Training*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 277-289, 2007.

- [30] O. S. Pitan, "Towards enhancing university graduate employability in Nigeria," *Journal of Sociology and Social Anthropology*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1-11, 2016.
- [31] A. G. Watts, *Career development learning and employability*. New York: Higher Education Academy, 2006.
- [32] C. D. Lindsay, "The concept of employability and the experience of unemployment," *Doctoral Dissertation*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh Napier University, 2009.
- [33] F. Luthans, *Organizational behavior*. Boston: McGraw-Hill, 2008.
- [34] R. Kreitner and A. Kinichi, *Organization behavior*. Boston: Irwin/McGraw-Hill, 2003.
- [35] B. M. Bass, *Leadership and performance beyond expectations*. New York: The Free Press, 1985.
- [36] B. M. Bass, *Bass & Stogdill's handbook of leadership: Theory, research and managerial applications*. New York: The Free Press, 1990.
- [37] M. Fugate, A. J. Kinicki, and B. E. Ashforth, "Employability: A psycho-social construct, its dimensions, and applications," *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 14-38, 2004.
- [38] J. Griffith, "Relation of principal transformational leadership to school staff job satisfaction, staff turnover, and school performance," *Journal of Educational Administration*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 333-356, 2004.
- [39] K. Nielsen, J. Yarker, R. Randall, and F. Munir, "The mediating effects of team and self-efficacy on the relationship between transformational leadership, and job satisfaction and psychological well-being in healthcare professionals: A cross-sectional questionnaire survey," *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, vol. 46, no. 9, pp. 1236-1244, 2009.
- [40] S. Braun, C. Peus, S. Weisweiler, and D. Frey, "Transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and team performance: A multilevel mediation model of trust," *The Leadership Quarterly*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 270-283, 2013.
- [41] S. A. Boamah, H. K. S. Laschinger, C. Wong, and S. Clarke, "Effect of transformational leadership on job satisfaction and patient safety outcomes," *Nursing Outlook*, vol. 66, no. 2, pp. 180-189, 2018.
- [42] M. Eliophotou-Menon and A. Ioannou, "The link between transformational leadership and teachers' job satisfaction, commitment, motivation to learn, and trust in the leader," *Academy of Educational Leadership Journal*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 12-22, 2016.
- [43] K. Leithwood and D. Jantzi, "Linking leadership to student learning: The contributions of leader efficacy," *Educational Administration Quarterly*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 496-528, 2008.
- [44] S. Nguni, P. Slegers and E. Denessen, "Transformational and transactional leadership effects on teachers' job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior in primary schools: The tanzanian case," *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 145-177, 2006.
- [45] T. W. Ng, L. T. Eby, K. L. Sorensen, and D. C. Feldman, "Predictors of objective and subjective career success: a meta-analysis," *Personnel Psychology*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 367-408, 2005.
- [46] E. Berntson, N. K. Aswall and M. Sverke, "Investigating the relationship between employability and self-efficacy: a cross-lagged analysis," *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 413-425, 2008.
- [47] M. Frese and D. Fay, "Personal initiative: An active performance concept for work in the 21st century," *Research in Organizational Behavior*, vol. 23, pp. 133-187, 2001.
- [48] N. De Cuyper, G. Notelaers, and H. De Witte, "Job insecurity and employability in fixed-term contractors, agency workers, and permanent workers: Associations with job satisfaction and affective organizational commitment," *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 193-205, 2009.
- [49] T. W. Taris and M. A. Kompier, "Job characteristics and learning behavior: Review and psychological mechanisms," *Emerald Group Publishing Limited*, vol. 4, pp. 127-166, 2004.
- [50] N. D. De Cuyper, C. Bernhard-Oettel, E. Berntson, H. D. Witte, and B. Alarco, "Employability and employees' well-being: Mediation by job insecurity," *Applied Psychology*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 488-509, 2008.
- [51] Forrier and L. Sels, "The concept employability: A complex mosaic," *International Journal of Human Resources Development and Management*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 102-124, 2003.